

INTEGER GROUP DETERMINANTS FOR C_4^2

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Abstract

We give a complete description of the integer group determinant for C_4^2 , where C_4 is the cyclic group of order 4.

1. Introduction

At the meeting of the American Mathematical Society in Hayward, California, in April 1977, Olga Taussky-Todd [11] asked if one could characterize the values that can be obtained as the determinant of an integer circulant matrix [3, 4]. This is the same as asking for the values obtained by the group determinant for a cyclic group when it is evaluated on integers. One may ask the same question for any finite group, not just for the cyclic groups.

Recall that for a finite group G , assigning a variable x_g for each $g \in G$, the group determinant of G is defined as $\det (x_{gh^{-1}})_{g,h \in G}$. The group determinant is called an integer group determinant of G when the all variables x_g are integers. We denote the set of all integer group determinants of G by $S(G)$:

$$S(G) := \left\{ \det (x_{gh^{-1}})_{g,h \in G} \mid x_g \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}.$$

For every group G of order at most 15, $S(G)$ was determined (see [6, 8]). Let C_n be the cyclic group of order n and D_n be the dihedral group of order n . For the groups of order 16, the complete descriptions of $S(G)$ were obtained for D_{16} [1, Theorem 5.3], C_{16} [17], C_2^4 [18] and $C_8 \times C_2$ [13, Theorem 1.5]. In this paper, we determine $S(C_4^2)$.

Theorem 1. *Let $P := \{p \mid p \equiv -3 \pmod{8}\}$ is a prime number} and*

$$A := \{(8k - 3)(8l - 3)(8m - 3)(8n - 3) \mid \\ k \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l - 3, 8m - 3, 8n - 3 \in P, k + l \not\equiv m + n \pmod{2}\} \\ \subsetneq \{16m - 7 \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

Then we have

$$S(C_4^2) = \{16m + 1, 2^{15}p(2m + 1), 2^{16}m \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}, p \in P\} \cup A.$$

There are fourteen groups of order 16 up to isomorphism [2, 19], and five of them are abelian. Our result leaves $C_4 \times C_2^2$ as the only abelian group of order 16 for which $S(G)$ has not been determined (this group and all of the non-abelian groups of order 16 have recently been resolved as well [5, 9, 10, 12, 15, 16] and [7, Theorems 3.1 and 4.1]).

2. Preliminaries

For any $\bar{r} \in C_n$ with $r \in \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$, we denote the variable $x_{\bar{r}}$ by x_r , and let

$$D_n(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}) := \det (x_{gh^{-1}})_{g,h \in C_n}.$$

For any $(\bar{r}, \bar{s}) \in C_4^2$ with $r, s \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, we denote the variable $y_{(\bar{r}, \bar{s})}$ by y_j , where $j := r + 4s$, and let

$$D_{4 \times 4}(y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{15}) := \det (y_{gh^{-1}})_{g,h \in C_4^2}.$$

From the $G = C_4$ and $H = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}\}$ case of [13, Theorem 1.1], we have the following corollary.

Corollary 1. *We have*

$$D_4(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) = D_2(x_0 + x_2, x_1 + x_3)D_2(x_0 - x_2, \sqrt{-1}(x_1 - x_3)) \\ = \{(x_0 + x_2)^2 - (x_1 + x_3)^2\} \{(x_0 - x_2)^2 + (x_1 - x_3)^2\}.$$

Remark 1. From Corollary 1, we have $D_4(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) = -D_4(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_0)$.

From the $H = K = C_4$ case of [14, Theorem 1.1], we have the following corollary.

Corollary 2. *Let $D := D_{4 \times 4}(y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{15})$. Then we have*

$$D = \prod_{k=0}^3 D_4 \left(\sum_{s=0}^3 \sqrt{-1}^{ks} y_{4s}, \sum_{s=0}^3 \sqrt{-1}^{ks} y_{1+4s}, \sum_{s=0}^3 \sqrt{-1}^{ks} y_{2+4s}, \sum_{s=0}^3 \sqrt{-1}^{ks} y_{3+4s} \right).$$

Throughout this paper, we assume that $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{15} \in \mathbb{Z}$, and let

$$\begin{aligned} b_i &:= (a_i + a_{i+8}) + (a_{i+4} + a_{i+12}), & 0 \leq i \leq 3, \\ c_i &:= (a_i + a_{i+8}) - (a_{i+4} + a_{i+12}), & 0 \leq i \leq 3, \\ d_i &:= a_i - a_{i+8}, & 0 \leq i \leq 7, \\ \alpha_i &:= d_i + \sqrt{-1}d_{i+4}, & 0 \leq i \leq 3. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2. For any $0 \leq i \leq 3$, the following hold:

- (1) $b_i \equiv c_i \equiv d_i + d_{i+4} \pmod{2}$;
- (2) $b_i + c_i \equiv 2d_i \pmod{4}$;
- (3) $b_i - c_i \equiv 2d_{i+4} \pmod{4}$.

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} &:= (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{15}), & \mathbf{b} &:= (b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3), & \mathbf{c} &:= (c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3), \\ \beta &:= (\alpha_0 + \alpha_2)^2 - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3)^2, & \gamma &:= (\alpha_0 - \alpha_2)^2 + (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3)^2. \end{aligned}$$

From Corollaries 1 and 2, we have the following relation which will be frequently used in this paper:

$$D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) = D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma},$$

where $\bar{\alpha}$ denotes the complex conjugate of $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$. From

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= (\alpha_0 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_3)(\alpha_0 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_3) \\ &= \{(d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3) + \sqrt{-1}(d_4 + d_6 + d_5 + d_7)\} \\ &\quad \times \{(d_0 + d_2 - d_1 - d_3) + \sqrt{-1}(d_4 + d_6 - d_5 - d_7)\}, \\ \gamma &= \{(\alpha_0 - \alpha_2) + \sqrt{-1}(\alpha_1 - \alpha_3)\} \{(\alpha_0 - \alpha_2) - \sqrt{-1}(\alpha_1 - \alpha_3)\} \\ &= \{(d_0 - d_2 - d_5 + d_7) + \sqrt{-1}(d_4 - d_6 + d_1 - d_3)\} \\ &\quad \times \{(d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7) + \sqrt{-1}(d_4 - d_6 - d_1 + d_3)\}, \end{aligned}$$

we have the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *The following hold:*

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta} &= \{(d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3)^2 + (d_4 + d_6 + d_5 + d_7)^2\} \\ &\quad \times \{(d_0 + d_2 - d_1 - d_3)^2 + (d_4 + d_6 - d_5 - d_7)^2\}, \\ \gamma\bar{\gamma} &= \{(d_0 - d_2 - d_5 + d_7)^2 + (d_4 - d_6 + d_1 - d_3)^2\} \\ &\quad \times \{(d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7)^2 + (d_4 - d_6 - d_1 + d_3)^2\}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3. From Lemma 1, each $\beta\bar{\beta}$ and $\gamma\bar{\gamma}$ is invariant under the replacing of $(d_0, \dots, d_7)$ with $(d_4, d_5, d_6, d_7, d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3)$.

Lemma 2. *We have $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) \equiv D_4(\mathbf{b}) \equiv D_4(\mathbf{c}) \equiv \beta\bar{\beta} \equiv \gamma\bar{\gamma} \pmod{2}$.*

Proof. From Corollary 1, it follows that for any $x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3 \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$D_4(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \equiv x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \pmod{2}.$$

Also, from Lemma 1, we have

$$\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv d_0 + d_1 + \dots + d_7 \equiv \gamma\bar{\gamma} \pmod{2}.$$

Therefore, from Remark 2 (1), we have $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \equiv D_4(\mathbf{c}) \equiv \beta\bar{\beta} \equiv \gamma\bar{\gamma} \pmod{2}$. □

The following lemma is immediately obtained from Lemma 1.

Lemma 3. *We have*

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta} &= \{(d_0 + d_2)^2 + (d_4 + d_6)^2 + (d_1 + d_3)^2 + (d_5 + d_7)^2\}^2 \\ &\quad - 4\{(d_0 + d_2)(d_1 + d_3) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_5 + d_7)\}^2, \\ \gamma\bar{\gamma} &= \{(d_0 - d_2)^2 + (d_4 - d_6)^2 + (d_1 - d_3)^2 + (d_5 - d_7)^2\}^2 \\ &\quad - 4\{(d_0 - d_2)(d_5 - d_7) - (d_4 - d_6)(d_1 - d_3)\}^2. \end{aligned}$$

By direct calculation, we have the following lemma.

Lemma 4. *We have*

$$\begin{aligned} &\{(d_0 + d_2)^2 + (d_4 + d_6)^2 + (d_1 + d_3)^2 + (d_5 + d_7)^2\}^2 \\ &\quad - \{(d_0 - d_2)^2 + (d_4 - d_6)^2 + (d_1 - d_3)^2 + (d_5 - d_7)^2\}^2 \\ &= 8(d_0^2 + d_2^2 + d_4^2 + d_6^2 + d_1^2 + d_3^2 + d_5^2 + d_7^2)(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7). \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 5. *The following hold:*

- (1) $2(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \equiv b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \pmod{4}$;
- (2) $2(d_0d_7 + d_2d_5 + d_4d_3 + d_6d_1) \equiv b_0b_3 + b_2b_1 - c_0c_3 - c_2c_1 \pmod{4}$;
- (3) $2(d_0d_3 + d_2d_1 + d_4d_7 + d_6d_5) \equiv b_0b_3 + b_2b_1 + c_0c_3 + c_2c_1 \pmod{4}$;
- (4) $2(d_0d_5 + d_2d_7 + d_4d_1 + d_6d_3) \equiv b_0b_1 + b_2b_3 - c_0c_1 - c_2c_3 \pmod{4}$;
- (5) $2(d_0d_1 + d_2d_3 + d_4d_5 + d_6d_7) \equiv b_0b_1 + b_2b_3 + c_0c_1 + c_2c_3 \pmod{4}$.

Proof. We obtain (1) from

$$\begin{aligned} b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 &= (a_0 + a_8 + a_4 + a_{12})(a_2 + a_{10} + a_6 + a_{14}) \\ &\quad + (a_1 + a_9 + a_5 + a_{13})(a_3 + a_{11} + a_7 + a_{15}) \\ &\quad + (a_0 + a_8 - a_4 - a_{12})(a_2 + a_{10} - a_6 - a_{14}) \\ &\quad + (a_1 + a_9 - a_5 - a_{13})(a_3 + a_{11} - a_7 - a_{15}) \\ &= 2(a_0 + a_8)(a_2 + a_{10}) + 2(a_4 + a_{12})(a_6 + a_{14}) \\ &\quad + 2(a_1 + a_9)(a_3 + a_{11}) + 2(a_5 + a_{13})(a_7 + a_{15}) \\ &\equiv 2(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, we can prove (2)–(5). □

Let $P := \{p \mid p \equiv -3 \pmod{8} \text{ is a prime number}\}$. It is well known that a positive integer n is expressible as a sum of two squares if and only if in the prime factorization of n , every prime of the form $4k + 3$ occurs an even number of times. From this, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3. *If $a^2 + b^2 \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$, then there exist $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $8l - 3 \in P$ satisfying $a^2 + b^2 = (8k + 1)(8l - 3)$.*

3. Integer Group Determinant of C_4

Lemma 6 ([13, Lemmas 4.6 and 4.7]). *For any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the following hold:*

- (1) $D_4(2k + 1, 2l, 2m, 2n) \equiv 8m + 1 \pmod{16}$;
- (2) $D_4(2k, 2l + 1, 2m + 1, 2n + 1) \equiv 8(k + l + n) - 3 \pmod{16}$.

Let $\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ be the set of all odd numbers.

Lemma 7. *For any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the following hold:*

- (1) $D_4(2k, 2l, 2m, 2n) \in \begin{cases} 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k + m \not\equiv l + n \pmod{2}, \\ 2^8\mathbb{Z}, & k + m \equiv l + n \pmod{2}; \end{cases}$
- (2) $D_4(2k + 1, 2l + 1, 2m + 1, 2n + 1) \in \begin{cases} 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k + m \not\equiv l + n \pmod{2}, \\ 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (k + m)(l + n) \equiv -1 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^9\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise}; \end{cases}$
- (3) $D_4(2k, 2l + 1, 2m, 2n + 1) \in \begin{cases} 2^5\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k - m \equiv l - n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2^6\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k \equiv m \pmod{2}, (2k + 2l + 1)(2m + 2n + 1) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}, \\ 2^7\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise}; \end{cases}$

$$(4) \ D_4(2k, 2l, 2m + 1, 2n + 1) \in \begin{cases} 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (2k + 2m + 1)(2l + 2n + 1) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}, \\ 2^5\mathbb{Z}, & (2k + 2m + 1)(2l + 2n + 1) \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8}. \end{cases}$$

To prove Lemma 7, we remark the following.

Remark 4 ([18, Remark 3.5]). For any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the following hold:

- (1) $(2k + 2l + 1)(2m + 2n + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ if and only if $k - m \equiv -l + n \pmod{4}$;
- (2) $(2k + 2l + 1)(2m + 2n + 1) \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$ if and only if $k + m \equiv -l - n - 1 \pmod{4}$;
- (3) $(2k + 2l + 1)(2m + 2n + 1) \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ if and only if $k + m \equiv 1 - l - n \pmod{4}$;
- (4) $(2k + 2l + 1)(2m + 2n + 1) \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$ if and only if $k - m \equiv 2 - l + n \pmod{4}$.

Proof of Lemma 7. We obtain (1) from

$$\begin{aligned} D_4(2k, 2l, 2m, 2n) &= \{(2k + 2m)^2 - (2l + 2n)^2\} \{(2k - 2m)^2 + (2l - 2n)^2\} \\ &= 2^4 \{(k + m)^2 - (l + n)^2\} \{(k - m)^2 + (l - n)^2\}. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain (2) from

$$\begin{aligned} D_4(2k + 1, 2l + 1, 2m + 1, 2n + 1) &= \{(2k + 2m + 2)^2 - (2l + 2n + 2)^2\} \{(2k - 2m)^2 + (2l - 2n)^2\} \\ &= 2^4 \{(k + m + 1)^2 - (l + n + 1)^2\} \{(k - m)^2 + (l - n)^2\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$(k + m + 1)^2 - (l + n + 1)^2 \in \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k + m \not\equiv l + n \pmod{2}, \\ 2^2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (k + m)(l + n) \equiv -1 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^4\mathbb{Z}, & (k + m)(l + n) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^3\mathbb{Z}, & k + m \equiv l + n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \end{cases}$$

$$(k - m)^2 + (l - n)^2 \in \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k + m \not\equiv l + n \pmod{2}, \\ 2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k + m \equiv l + n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2^2\mathbb{Z}, & k + m \equiv l + n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

We prove (3). From Remark 4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(k+m)^2 - (l+n+1)^2\} \{(k-m)^2 + (l-n)^2\} \\ & \in \begin{cases} 2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & k-m \equiv l-n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \\ 2^3\mathbb{Z}, & k \not\equiv m, l \equiv n \pmod{2}, \\ 2^3\mathbb{Z}, & \text{when (I)}, \\ 2^2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & \text{when (II)}, \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\text{(I) } k \equiv m \pmod{2} \text{ and } (2k+2l+1)(2m+2n+1) \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8};$$

$$\text{(II) } k \equiv m \pmod{2} \text{ and } (2k+2l+1)(2m+2n+1) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}.$$

Therefore, (3) is obtained from

$$\begin{aligned} & D_4(2k, 2l+1, 2m, 2n+1) \\ & = \{(2k+2m)^2 - (2l+2n+2)^2\} \{(2k-2m)^2 + (2l-2n)^2\} \\ & = 2^4 \{(k+m)^2 - (l+n+1)^2\} \{(k-m)^2 + (l-n)^2\}. \end{aligned}$$

We prove (4). From Remark 4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} k+m-l-n & \in \begin{cases} 2^2\mathbb{Z}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv 1 \pmod{8}, \\ \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv -1 \text{ or } 3 \pmod{8}, \\ 2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv -3 \pmod{8}, \end{cases} \\ k+m+l+n+1 & \in \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv 1 \text{ or } -3 \pmod{8}, \\ 2^2\mathbb{Z}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv -1 \pmod{8}, \\ 2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (2k+2m+1)(2l+2n+1) \equiv 3 \pmod{8}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, (4) is obtained from

$$\begin{aligned} & D_4(2k, 2l, 2m+1, 2n+1) \\ & = \{(2k+2m+1)^2 - (2l+2n+1)^2\} \{(2k-2m-1)^2 + (2l-2n-1)^2\} \\ & = 2^3(k+m+l+n+1)(k+m-l-n) \\ & \quad \times \{2(k-m)(k-m-1) + 2(l-n)(l-n-1) + 1\}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

4. Odd Values Must Be of the Stated Form

In this section, we prove that the odd values must be of the stated form. Let

$$\begin{aligned} A & := \{(8k-3)(8l-3)(8m-3)(8n-3) \mid \\ & k \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l-3, 8m-3, 8n-3 \in P, k+l \not\equiv m+n \pmod{2}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 8. We have $S(C_4^2) \cap \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}} \subset \{16m + 1 \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}\} \cup A$.

To prove Lemma 8, we use the following five lemmas.

Lemma 9. Let $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$. Then we have the following:

(1) If $(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3, c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \equiv (0, 0)$ or $(2, 2) \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k + 1)(8l + 1) \mid k, l \in \mathbb{Z}, k \equiv l \pmod{2}\};$$

(2) If $(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3, c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \equiv (0, 2)$ or $(2, 0) \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k + 1)(8l + 1) \mid k, l \in \mathbb{Z}, k \not\equiv l \pmod{2}\};$$

(3) If $(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3, c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \equiv (1, 1)$ or $(-1, -1) \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k - 3)(8l - 3) \mid k, l \in \mathbb{Z}, k \equiv l \pmod{2}\};$$

(4) If $(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3, c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \equiv (1, -1)$ or $(-1, 1) \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k - 3)(8l - 3) \mid k, l \in \mathbb{Z}, k \not\equiv l \pmod{2}\}.$$

Proof. First, we prove (1) and (2). If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then exactly three of b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 are even. On the other hand, for any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$m \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ if and only if } (2k + 1)(2m) + (2l)(2n) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}.$$

Therefore, from Remarks 1 and 2 (1) and Lemma 6 (1), we have (1) and (2). Next, we prove (3) and (4). If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then exactly one of b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 is even. On the other hand, for any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$k + l + n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ if and only if } (2k)(2m + 1) + (2l + 1)(2n + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{4}.$$

Therefore, from Remarks 1 and 2 (1) and Lemma 6 (2), we have (3) and (4). $\square$

The following lemma is immediately obtained from Lemma 9.

Lemma 10. If $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \equiv 1 - 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}.$$

Lemma 11. Let $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$. Then the following hold:

(1) If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k - 3)(8l - 3) \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l - 3 \in P, k \not\equiv l \pmod{2}\};$$

(2) If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{(8k-3)(8l-3) \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l-3 \in P, k \equiv l \pmod{2}\}.$$

Proof. From $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$ and Remark 2 (1), $d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \not\equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \pmod{2}$ holds. Moreover, from $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$ and Lemma 3, exactly one of $d_0 + d_2, d_1 + d_3, d_4 + d_6, d_5 + d_7$ is even. For any $k, l \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) = (8k-3)(8l-3)$, it follows from Lemma 10 that $k \not\equiv l \pmod{2}$ if $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$; $k \equiv l \pmod{2}$ if $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Below, we prove that there exist $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $8l-3 \in P$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) = (8k-3)(8l-3)$. First, suppose that $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Then, exactly three of b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 are even. From Remark 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) &= D_4(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_0)D_4(c_1, c_2, c_3, c_0) \\ &= D_4(b_2, b_3, b_0, b_1)D_4(c_2, c_3, c_0, c_1) \\ &= D_4(b_3, b_0, b_1, b_2)D_4(c_3, c_0, c_1, c_2). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Remark 2 (1), we may assume without loss of generality that $\mathbf{b} \equiv \mathbf{c} \equiv (1, 0, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$. From Remark 2, we have

$$2(d_1 + d_3) \equiv b_1 + b_3 + c_1 + c_3 \equiv b_1 + b_3 - c_1 - c_3 \equiv 2(d_5 + d_7) \pmod{4}.$$

Thus, $d_1 + d_3$ must be odd since $d_1 + d_3 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \pmod{2}$. Hence, from $b_1 + b_3 + c_1 + c_3 \equiv 2(d_1 + d_3) \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, we have $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (0, 2)$ or $(2, 0) \pmod{4}$. We consider the case of $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (0, 2) \pmod{4}$. From $\mathbf{b} \equiv (1, 0, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$ and Lemma 6 (1), there exists $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{b}) = 8j + 1$. On the other hand, from $\mathbf{c} \equiv (1, 0, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$ and $c_1 + c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, we have $c_1 - c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Thus, from Corollary 3, there exist $l' \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l-3 \in P$ satisfying $(c_0 - c_2)^2 + (c_1 - c_3)^2 = (8l' + 1)(8l - 3)$. Also, there exists $k' \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $(c_0 + c_2)^2 - (c_1 + c_3)^2 = 8k' - 3$. From Corollary 1, we have $D_4(\mathbf{c}) = (8k' - 3)(8l' + 1)(8l - 3)$. Therefore, there exists $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) = (8k - 3)(8l - 3)$. In the same way, the case of $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (2, 0) \pmod{4}$ can also be proved.

Next, suppose that $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then, exactly one of b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 is even. From Remarks 1 and 2 (1), we may assume without loss of generality that $\mathbf{b} \equiv \mathbf{c} \equiv (0, 1, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$. In the same way as in the above, we have $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (0, 2)$ or $(2, 0) \pmod{4}$. We consider the case of $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (0, 2) \pmod{4}$. From $\mathbf{c} \equiv (0, 1, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$ and Lemma 6 (2), there exists $k' \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{c}) = 8k' - 3$. On the other hand, from $\mathbf{b} \equiv (0, 1, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$ and $b_1 + b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, we have $b_1 - b_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Thus, from Corollary 3, there exist $l' \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l-3 \in P$ satisfying $(b_0 - b_2)^2 + (b_1 - b_3)^2 = (8l' + 1)(8l - 3)$. Also, there exists $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $(b_0 + b_2)^2 - (b_1 + b_3)^2 = 8j + 1$. From Corollary 1, we have $D_4(\mathbf{b}) = (8j + 1)(8l' + 1)(8l - 3)$. Therefore, there exists $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) = (8k - 3)(8l - 3)$. In the same way, the case of $(b_1 + b_3, c_1 + c_3) \equiv (2, 0) \pmod{4}$ can also be proved. $\square$

Lemma 12. *Let $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$. Then we have*

$$\beta\bar{\beta} - \gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}.$$

Proof. From Remark 2 (1), we have $d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \not\equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \pmod{2}$. Thus, $d_0^2 + d_2^2 + d_4^2 + d_6^2 + d_1^2 + d_3^2 + d_5^2 + d_7^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Also, since exactly one or three of $d_0 + d_2, d_4 + d_6, d_1 + d_3, d_5 + d_7$ are even, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(d_0 + d_2)(d_1 + d_3) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_5 + d_7)\}^2 \\ & \equiv \{(d_0 - d_2)(d_5 - d_7) - (d_4 - d_6)(d_1 - d_3)\}^2 \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

From the above and Lemmas 3, 4 and 5 (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta} - \gamma\bar{\gamma} & \equiv 8(d_0^2 + d_2^2 + d_4^2 + d_6^2 + d_1^2 + d_3^2 + d_5^2 + d_7^2)(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \\ & \equiv 8(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \\ & \equiv 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 13. *Let $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$. Then the following hold:*

(1) *If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} & \in \{(8j + 1)(8m - 3)(8n - 3) \mid \\ & j \in \mathbb{Z}, 8m - 3, 8n - 3 \in P, j \equiv m + n \pmod{2}\}; \end{aligned}$$

(2) *If $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} & \in \{(8j + 1)(8m - 3)(8n - 3) \mid \\ & j \in \mathbb{Z}, 8m - 3, 8n - 3 \in P, j \not\equiv m + n \pmod{2}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Remark 2 (1) and Lemma 12, we have $\gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv \beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$. Therefore, from Corollary 3, there exist $m', n' \in \mathbb{Z}, 8m - 3, 8n - 3 \in P$ satisfying

$$\beta\bar{\beta} = (8m' + 1)(8m - 3), \quad \gamma\bar{\gamma} = (8n' + 1)(8n - 3).$$

Let $j := 8m'n' + m' + n'$. Then, $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} = (8j + 1)(8m - 3)(8n - 3)$. From Lemma 12,

$$8(m + m' + n + n') \equiv \beta\bar{\beta} - \gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}.$$

Therefore, we have $2(j + m + n) \equiv 2(m' + n' + m + n) \equiv b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \pmod{4}$. □

Proof of Lemma 8. Let $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) = D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Then, $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$ holds from $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in \mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and Corollary 1. Since $\beta\bar{\beta}$ is an odd

number expressible in the form $x^2 + y^2$, we have $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Therefore, from Lemma 12,

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} &\equiv \beta\bar{\beta} \{ \beta\bar{\beta} - 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \} \\ &\equiv (\beta\bar{\beta})^2 - 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}. \end{aligned}$$

From this and Lemma 10, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} &\equiv \{1 - 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3)\} \\ &\quad \times \{(\beta\bar{\beta})^2 - 4(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3)\} \\ &\equiv (\beta\bar{\beta})^2 - 8(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{16}. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, from Remark 2 (1), it follows that $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv (\beta\bar{\beta})^2 \pmod{16}$. Therefore, if $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, then $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) \in \{16m + 1 \mid m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. If $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$, then we have $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) \in A'$ from Lemmas 11 and 13, where

$$\begin{aligned} A' := \{ &(8j + 1)(8k - 3)(8l - 3)(8m - 3)(8n - 3) \mid \\ &j, k \in \mathbb{Z}, 8l - 3, 8m - 3, 8n - 3 \in P, j \not\equiv k + l + m + n \pmod{2} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A' = A$, the lemma is proved. $\square$

5. Even Values Must Be of the Stated Form

In this section, we prove that the even values must be of the stated form.

Lemma 14. *The following hold:*

- (1) $S(C_4^2) \cap 2\mathbb{Z} \subset 2^{15}\mathbb{Z}$;
- (2) $S(C_4^2) \cap 2^{15}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}} \subset \{2^{15}p(2m + 1) \mid p \in P, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.

To prove Lemma 14, we use the following five lemmas.

Lemma 15. *The following hold:*

- (1) *If $b_0 \equiv b_1 \equiv b_2 \equiv b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then*

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \begin{cases} 2^8\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^{12}\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

- (2) *If $b_0 \equiv b_1 \equiv b_2 \equiv b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then*

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \begin{cases} 2^8\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

(3) If $b_0 \equiv b_2 \not\equiv b_1 \equiv b_3 \pmod{2}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \begin{cases} 2^{10}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & b_0 - b_2 \equiv b_1 - b_3 \equiv c_0 - c_2 \equiv c_1 - c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

(4) If $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \begin{cases} 2^8\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & (b_0 + b_2)(b_1 + b_3) \equiv \pm 3, (c_0 + c_2)(c_1 + c_3) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}, \\ 2^9\mathbb{Z}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. For any $k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\begin{aligned} k + m &\not\equiv l + n \pmod{2} \text{ if and only if } 2k + 2l + 2m + 2n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ k - m &\equiv l - n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ if and only if } 2k - 2m \equiv 2l - 2n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Remarks 1 and 2 (1) and Lemma 7, the lemma is proved. □

Lemma 16. *The following hold:*

(1) If $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then

$$\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \begin{cases} 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \not\equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^8\mathbb{Z}, & b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod{4}; \end{cases}$$

(2) If $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then

$$\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \begin{cases} 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & d \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^8\mathbb{Z}, & d \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} d := & \{(d_0 + d_2)(d_5 + d_7) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_1 + d_3)\} \\ & \times \{(d_0 - d_2)(d_1 - d_3) + (d_4 - d_6)(d_5 - d_7)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We prove (1). Let $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Then, from Remark 2 (1), we have $d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Also, from Remark 2 (1) and (2), $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod{4}$ if and only if

$$2(d_0 + d_2) \equiv b_0 + b_2 + c_0 + c_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 + c_1 + c_3 \equiv 2(d_1 + d_3) \pmod{4}.$$

Therefore, if $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \not\equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod{4}$, then $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_4 + d_6 \not\equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \pmod{2}$. Thus, from Lemma 1, we have $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. If

$b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod{4}$, then $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \pmod{2}$. Thus, from Lemma 1, we have $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^8\mathbb{Z}$.

We prove (2). Let $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then, from Remark 2 (1), we have $d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. From Remark 3, we may assume without loss of generality that $d_0 + d_2 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. We divide the proof into the following two cases:

- (i) $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$;
- (ii) $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

We remark that if (i), then $d \equiv d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3 \pmod{4}$ holds, and if (ii), then $d \equiv d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7 \pmod{4}$ holds. First, suppose that (i) holds. Then, from Lemma 1, we have $\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Also, from

$$\begin{aligned} (d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3, d_0 + d_2 - d_1 - d_3) &\equiv (0, 0) \text{ or } (2, 2) \pmod{4}, \\ (d_4 + d_6 + d_5 + d_7, d_4 + d_6 - d_5 - d_7) &\equiv (0, 2) \text{ or } (2, 0) \pmod{4} \end{aligned}$$

and Lemma 1, we have

$$\beta\bar{\beta} \in \begin{cases} 2^5\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & d \equiv d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^6\mathbb{Z}, & d \equiv d_0 + d_2 + d_1 + d_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Next, suppose that (ii) holds. Then, from Lemma 1, we have $\beta\bar{\beta} \in 2^2\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Also, from

$$\begin{aligned} (d_0 - d_2 - d_5 + d_7, d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7) &\equiv (0, 0) \text{ or } (2, 2) \pmod{4}, \\ (d_4 - d_6 + d_1 - d_3, d_4 - d_6 - d_1 + d_3) &\equiv (0, 2) \text{ or } (2, 0) \pmod{4} \end{aligned}$$

and Lemma 1, we have

$$\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \begin{cases} 2^5\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}, & d \equiv d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ 2^6\mathbb{Z}, & d \equiv d_0 - d_2 + d_5 - d_7 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

This completes the proof. □

Lemma 17. *The following hold:*

- (1) *If $b_0 \equiv b_1 \equiv b_2 \equiv b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$, then*

$$b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4};$$

- (2) *If $b_0 \equiv b_2 \not\equiv b_1 \equiv b_3 \pmod{2}$, $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$, then*

$$b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}.$$

Proof. We prove (1). Let $b_0 \equiv b_1 \equiv b_2 \equiv b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod 2$ and $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Then, from Remark 2 (1) and Lemma 7, one of the following cases holds:

- (i) $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$;
- (ii) $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$.

If (i), then $b_0 + b_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod 4$ and $c_0 + c_2 \equiv c_1 + c_3 \equiv 0 \pmod 4$ hold. Therefore, $(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3, c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \equiv (0, 2) \pmod 4$ holds. Thus, we have $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod 4$. In the same way, the case (ii) can also be proved. We prove (2). Let $b_0 \equiv b_2 \not\equiv b_1 \equiv b_3 \pmod 2$, $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Then, from Remarks 1 and 2 (1), we may assume without loss of generality that $\mathbf{b} \equiv \mathbf{c} \equiv (0, 1, 0, 1) \pmod 2$. From Lemma 7, either one of the following cases holds:

- (iii) $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in 2^5\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^6\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$;
- (iv) $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in 2^6\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^5\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$.

If (iii), then $b_0 - b_2 \equiv b_1 - b_3 \equiv 2 \pmod 4$ and $c_0 \equiv c_2 \equiv 0$ or $2 \pmod 4$ hold. Therefore, $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 \equiv -1 \pmod 4$ and $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \equiv 2 \pmod 4$ hold. Also, since $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \not\equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod 4$ from Lemma 16, it follows that $c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv -1 \pmod 4$ holds. Thus, we have $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod 4$. In the same way, the case (iv) can also be proved. □

Lemma 18. *Suppose that $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod 2$, $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod 4$. Then $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \{2^4p(2m+1) \mid p \in P, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.*

Proof. Since $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 0 \pmod 2$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$, from Remark 2 (1), we have

$$d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \equiv 0 \pmod 2.$$

On the other hand, from Lemma 16, we have $b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3 \not\equiv c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 \pmod 4$. From this and Remark 2 (1) and (2), we have

$$2d_0 + 2d_2 \equiv b_0 + b_2 + c_0 + c_2 \not\equiv b_1 + b_3 + c_1 + c_3 \equiv 2d_1 + 2d_3 \pmod 4.$$

Thus, $d_0 + d_2 \not\equiv d_1 + d_3 \pmod 2$. From the above, we have $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_4 + d_6 \not\equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \pmod 2$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(d_0 + d_2)(d_1 + d_3) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_5 + d_7)\}^2 \\ & \quad - \{(d_0 - d_2)(d_5 - d_7) - (d_4 - d_6)(d_1 - d_3)\}^2 \\ & \equiv 4(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \pmod 8, \\ & (d_0^2 + d_2^2 + d_4^2 + d_6^2 + d_1^2 + d_3^2 + d_5^2 + d_7^2)(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \equiv 0 \pmod 4. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Lemmas 3, 4 and 5 (1),

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\bar{\beta} - \gamma\bar{\gamma} &\equiv 8(d_0^2 + d_2^2 + d_4^2 + d_6^2 + d_1^2 + d_3^2 + d_5^2 + d_7^2)(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \\ &\quad + 16(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \\ &\equiv 16(d_0d_2 + d_4d_6 + d_1d_3 + d_5d_7) \\ &\equiv 8(b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3) \pmod{32}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $b_0b_2 + b_1b_3 + c_0c_2 + c_1c_3 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, we have $\beta\bar{\beta} - \gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv 16 \pmod{32}$. Note that $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 4$ or $-12 \pmod{32}$ since $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 4 \pmod{16}$ from Lemma 3. If $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 4 \pmod{32}$, then $\gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv 4 - 16 \equiv -12 \pmod{32}$. This implies that $\gamma\bar{\gamma}$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. If $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv -12 \pmod{32}$, then $\beta\bar{\beta}$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. $\square$

Lemma 19. *Suppose that $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^8\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Then $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \{2^{15}p(2m + 1) \mid p \in P, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}$.*

Proof. From Lemmas 15 and 16, we have

$$(b_0 + b_2)(b_1 + b_3) \equiv \pm 3, \quad (c_0 + c_2)(c_1 + c_3) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}, \quad d \equiv 2 \pmod{4},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} d &:= \{(d_0 + d_2)(d_5 + d_7) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_1 + d_3)\} \\ &\quad \times \{(d_0 - d_2)(d_1 - d_3) + (d_4 - d_6)(d_5 - d_7)\}. \end{aligned}$$

We divide the proof into the following cases:

- (i) $(b_0b_3 + b_2b_1, c_0c_3 + c_2c_1) \equiv (0, 0), (0, 2)$ or $(2, 0) \pmod{4}$;
- (ii) $(b_0b_3 + b_2b_1, c_0c_3 + c_2c_1) \equiv (2, 2) \pmod{4}$;
- (iii) $(b_0b_1 + b_2b_3, c_0c_1 + c_2c_3) \equiv (0, 0), (0, 2)$ or $(2, 0) \pmod{4}$;
- (iv) $(b_0b_1 + b_2b_3, c_0c_1 + c_2c_3) \equiv (2, 2) \pmod{4}$.

First, we consider the case (i). If $b_0b_3 + b_2b_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, then

$$(b_0 - b_2)(b_1 - b_3) = (b_0 + b_2)(b_1 + b_3) - 2(b_0b_3 + b_2b_1) \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}.$$

Thus, $(b_0 - b_2)^2 + (b_1 - b_3)^2 \equiv -6 \pmod{16}$. It implies that $(b_0 - b_2)^2 + (b_1 - b_3)^2$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. That is, $D_4(\mathbf{b})$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. In the same way, we can prove that $D_4(\mathbf{c})$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$ when $c_0c_3 + c_2c_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. Therefore, if (i), then

$$D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in \{2^8p(2m + 1) \mid p \in P, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

We can obtain the same conclusion for the case (iii). Next, we consider the case (ii). From $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and Remark 2 (1), we have $d_0 + d_2 + d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 + d_5 + d_7 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. From Remark 3, we may assume without loss of generality that $d_0 + d_2 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then, either one of the following cases holds:

(ii-1) $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$;

(ii-2) $d_0 + d_2 \equiv d_5 + d_7 \equiv 0, d_4 + d_6 \equiv d_1 + d_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Suppose that (ii) and (ii-1) hold. Then, from Lemma 5 (2), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (d_0 - d_2) + (d_1 - d_3) &\equiv (d_0 - d_2)(d_5 - d_7) + (d_4 - d_6)(d_1 - d_3) \\ &\equiv (d_0 + d_2)(d_5 + d_7) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_1 + d_3) \\ &\quad + 2(d_0d_7 + d_2d_5 + d_4d_3 + d_6d_1) \\ &\equiv d + (b_0b_3 + b_2b_1) - (c_0c_3 + c_2c_1) \\ &\equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Lemma 3, we have $\gamma\bar{\gamma} \equiv 4 - 16 \equiv -12 \pmod{32}$. Thus, $\gamma\bar{\gamma}$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. Suppose that (ii) and (ii-2) hold. Then, from Lemma 5 (3), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (d_0 + d_2) + (d_5 + d_7) &\equiv (d_0 + d_2)(d_1 + d_3) + (d_4 + d_6)(d_5 + d_7) \\ &\equiv (d_0 - d_2)(d_1 - d_3) + (d_4 - d_6)(d_5 - d_7) \\ &\quad + 2(d_0d_3 + d_2d_1 + d_4d_7 + d_6d_5) \\ &\equiv d + (b_0b_3 + b_2b_1) + (c_0c_3 + c_2c_1) \\ &\equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Lemma 3, we have $\beta\bar{\beta} \equiv 4 - 16 \equiv -12 \pmod{32}$. Thus, $\beta\bar{\beta}$ has at least one prime factor of the form $8k - 3$. From the above, if (ii), then

$$\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in \{2^7 p(2m + 1) \mid p \in P, m \in \mathbb{Z}\}.$$

We can obtain the same conclusion for the case (iv) by using Lemma 5 (4) and (5). □

Proof of Lemma 14. We prove (1). Let $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) = D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c})\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2\mathbb{Z}$. Then, from Lemma 2, we have $D_4(\mathbf{b}) \in 2\mathbb{Z}$. Thus, $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \pmod{2}$ from Corollary 1. Therefore, from Lemmas 15 and 16, we obtain (1). We prove (2). Let $D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) \in 2^{15}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$. Then, from Lemmas 15 and 16, one of the following cases holds:

(i) $b_0 \equiv b_1 \equiv b_2 \equiv b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$;

(ii) $b_0 \equiv b_2 \not\equiv b_1 \equiv b_3 \pmod{2}$, $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^{11}\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^4\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$;

(iii) $b_0 + b_2 \equiv b_1 + b_3 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, $D_4(\mathbf{b})D_4(\mathbf{c}) \in 2^8\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$ and $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \in 2^7\mathbb{Z}_{\text{odd}}$.

Therefore, from Lemmas 17-19, we obtain (2). □

6. Achieving the Values

In this section, we complete the proof of Theorem 1. Lemmas 8 and 14 imply that $S(C_4^2)$ does not include every integer that is not mentioned in Lemmas 20–22.

Lemma 20. *For any $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, the following are elements of $S(C_4^2)$:*

- (1) $16m + 1$;
- (2) $2^{16}(4m + 1)$;
- (3) $2^{16}(4m - 1)$;
- (4) $2^{16}(2m)$.

Lemma 21. *For any $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, $16l - 3, 16m - 3, 16n - 3, 16l + 5, 16m + 5, 16n + 5 \in P$, the following are elements of $S(C_4^2)$:*

- (1) $(16k - 3)(16l + 5)(16m - 3)(16n - 3)$;
- (2) $(16k - 3)(16l + 5)(16m + 5)(16n + 5)$;
- (3) $(16k + 5)(16l - 3)(16m - 3)(16n - 3)$;
- (4) $(16k + 5)(16l - 3)(16m + 5)(16n + 5)$.

Lemma 22. *For any $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $p \in P$, we have $2^{15}p(2m + 1) \in S(C_4^2)$.*

Proof of Lemma 20. We obtain (1) from

$$\begin{aligned} D_{4 \times 4}(m + 1, m, \dots, m) &= D_4(4m + 1, 4m, 4m, 4m)D_4(1, 0, 0, 0)^3 \\ &= (8m + 1)^2 - (8m)^2 \\ &= 16m + 1. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain (2) from

$$\begin{aligned} &D_{4 \times 4}(m + 2, m, m, m, m, m, m + 1, m, m + 1, m, \dots, m) \\ &= D_4(4m + 3, 4m, 4m + 1, 4m)D_4(3, 0, -1, 0) \\ &\quad \times D_4(1, 0, \sqrt{-1}, 0)D_4(1, 0, -\sqrt{-1}, 0) \\ &= \{(8m + 4)^2 - (8m)^2\} \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot 4^2 \cdot (1 + \sqrt{-1})^4 (1 - \sqrt{-1})^4 \\ &= 2^{16}(4m + 1). \end{aligned}$$

We obtain (3) from

$$\begin{aligned} &D_{4 \times 4}(m + 1, m, m, m - 1, m, m - 1, m, m, m, m, m - 1, m, m - 1, m - 1, m) \\ &= D_4(4m + 1, 4m - 2, 4m - 1, 4m - 2) D_4(1, 2, 1, -2) \\ &\quad \times D_4(1, 0, \sqrt{-1}, 0) D_4(1, 0, -\sqrt{-1}, 0) \\ &= \{(8m)^2 - (8m - 4)^2\} \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot 4^2 \cdot (1 + \sqrt{-1})^4 (1 - \sqrt{-1})^4 \\ &= 2^{16}(4m - 1). \end{aligned}$$

We obtain (4) from

$$\begin{aligned} &D_{4 \times 4}(m + 1, m, m, m, m, m, m, m, m + 1, m - 1, m, m, m, m - 1, m, m) \\ &= D_4(4m + 2, 4m - 2, 4m, 4m) D_4(2, 0, 0, 0) \\ &\quad \times D_4(0, 1 + \sqrt{-1}, 0, 0) D_4(0, 1 - \sqrt{-1}, 0, 0) \\ &= \{(8m + 2)^2 - (8m - 2)^2\} \cdot 2^3 \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot (1 + \sqrt{-1})^4 (1 - \sqrt{-1})^4 \\ &= 2^{16}(2m). \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Remark 5. When

$$\begin{aligned} d_0 &= 2t - 2v, & d_1 &= 2t + 2w + 1, & d_2 &= 2t + 2v + 2e, & d_3 &= 2t - 2w, \\ d_4 &= 2u + 2w + 1, & d_5 &= 2u + 2v + 1, & d_6 &= 2u - 2w, & d_7 &= 2u - 2v, \end{aligned}$$

where $e \in \{0, 1\}$, from Lemma 1, we have

$$\beta \bar{\beta} \gamma \bar{\gamma} = \{(8t + 2e + 1)^2 + (8u + 2)^2\} \{(8v + 2e + 1)^2 + (8w + 2)^2\}.$$

Proof of Lemma 21. We remark that for any $16m - 8e + 5, 16n - 8e + 5 \in P$ with $e \in \{0, 1\}$, there exist $t, u, v, w \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} 16m - 8e + 5 &= (8t + 2e + 1)^2 + (8u + 2)^2, \\ 16n - 8e + 5 &= (8v + 2e + 1)^2 + (8w + 2)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{*}$$

We prove (1) and (2). For any $16l + 5 \in P$, we can take $r, s \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying

$$16l + 5 = (8r + 1)^2 + (8s + 2)^2.$$

Also, we take t, u, v, w satisfying (*). Let

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= k - r + t - v, & a_1 &= k - s + t + w, & a_2 &= k + r + t + v + e, \\ a_3 &= k + s + t - w, & a_4 &= -k + r + u + w + 1, & a_5 &= -k + s + u + v + 1, \\ a_6 &= -k - r + u - w, & a_7 &= -k - s + u - v, & a_8 &= k - r - t + v, \\ a_9 &= k - s - t - w - 1, & a_{10} &= k + r - t - v - e, & a_{11} &= k + s - t + w, \\ a_{12} &= -k + r - u - w, & a_{13} &= -k + s - u - v, & a_{14} &= -k - r - u + w, \\ a_{15} &= -k - s - u + v. \end{aligned}$$

Then, from Remark 5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) &= D_4(1, 0, 0, 0)D_4(4k - 4r - 1, 4k - 4s - 2, 4k + 4r, 4k + 4s)\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \\ &= \{(8k - 1)^2 - (8k - 2)^2\} \{(8r + 1)^2 + (8s + 2)^2\} \\ &\quad \times \{(8t + 2e + 1)^2 + (8u + 2)^2\} \{(8v + 2e + 1)^2 + (8w + 2)^2\} \\ &= (16k - 3)(16l + 5)(16m - 8e + 5)(16n - 8e + 5). \end{aligned}$$

We prove (3) and (4). For any $16l - 3 \in P$, we can take $r, s \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying

$$16l - 3 = (8r + 3)^2 + (8s + 2)^2.$$

Also, we take t, u, v, w satisfying (*). Let

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= k + r + t - v + 1, & a_1 &= k + s + t + w + 1, & a_2 &= k - r + t + v + e, \\ a_3 &= k - s + t - w, & a_4 &= -k - r + u + w, & a_5 &= -k - s + u + v, \\ a_6 &= -k + r + u - w, & a_7 &= -k + s + u - v, & a_8 &= k + r - t + v + 1, \\ a_9 &= k + s - t - w, & a_{10} &= k - r - t - v - e, & a_{11} &= k - s - t + w, \\ a_{12} &= -k - r - u - w - 1, & a_{13} &= -k - s - u - v - 1, & a_{14} &= -k + r - u + w, \\ a_{15} &= -k + s - u + v. \end{aligned}$$

Then, from Remark 5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) &= D_4(1, 0, 0, 0)D_4(4k + 4r + 3, 4k + 4s + 2, 4k - 4r, 4k - 4s)\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \\ &= \{(8k + 3)^2 - (8k + 2)^2\} \{(8r + 3)^2 + (8s + 2)^2\} \\ &\quad \times \{(8t + 2e + 1)^2 + (8u + 2)^2\} \{(8v + 2e + 1)^2 + (8w + 2)^2\} \\ &= (16k + 5)(16l - 3)(16m - 8e + 5)(16n - 8e + 5). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Lemma 22. For any $p \in P$, there exist $r, s \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $2p = (8r + 3)^2 + (8s + 1)^2$. Let

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= m + r + 1, & a_1 &= m + r + 1, & a_2 &= m + r + 1, & a_3 &= m + r, \\ a_4 &= m + s, & a_5 &= m + s, & a_6 &= m + s + 1, & a_7 &= m + s, \\ a_8 &= m - r + 1, & a_9 &= m - r, & a_{10} &= m - r, & a_{11} &= m - r - 1, \\ a_{12} &= m - s, & a_{13} &= m - s, & a_{14} &= m - s, & a_{15} &= m - s. \end{aligned}$$

Then, from Lemma 1, we have $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} = 2^3 \{(8r + 3)^2 + (8s + 1)^2\} = 2^4p$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) &= D_4(4m + 2, 4m + 1, 4m + 2, 4m - 1)D_4(2, 1, 0, -1)\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \\ &= \{(8m + 4)^2 - (8m)^2\} \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot (2^2 + 2^2) \cdot 2^4p \\ &= 2^{15}p(4m + 1). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, let

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_0 &= m+r, & a_1 &= m+r, & a_2 &= m+r+1, & a_3 &= m+r, \\
 a_4 &= m+s, & a_5 &= m+s, & a_6 &= m+s, & a_7 &= m+s-1, \\
 a_8 &= m-r, & a_9 &= m-r-1, & a_{10} &= m-r, & a_{11} &= m-r-1, \\
 a_{12} &= m-s, & a_{13} &= m-s, & a_{14} &= m-s-1, & a_{15} &= m-s-1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, from Lemma 1, we have $\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} = 2^3 \{(8r+3)^2 + (8s+1)^2\} = 2^4 p$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4}(\mathbf{a}) &= D_4(4m, 4m-1, 4m, 4m-3)D_4(0, -1, 2, 1)\beta\bar{\beta}\gamma\bar{\gamma} \\
 &= \{(8m)^2 - (8m-4)^2\} \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot (2^2 + 2^2) \cdot 2^4 p \\
 &= 2^{15} p(4m-1). \qquad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

From Lemmas 8, 14 and 20–22, Theorem 1 is proved.

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